

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

USE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Abstract

In order for education to become a highly developed field, society must achieve a high level of training of the new generation in order to secure its future. This is clearly reflected in the Education Reforms Program of the Republic of Azerbaijan. For this, the content of education should be updated in terms of forming a new society. The creation of new learning technologies should be implemented as an urgent task. Using the possibilities of interactive methods, a wide space should be given to areas that stimulate the work of students and strengthen their interest in learning and reading. In the modernization of the education system, the diverse and wide application of information and communication technologies in the learning process has opened great opportunities and perspectives [1].

The cardinal changes taking place in humanity today lead to the acquisition of richer scientific knowledge, the creation of fundamentally new technologies, and the need for a new pedagogical approach to the methodology of teaching subjects. In the teaching of subjects at school, the application of Information Communication technologies opens up a wide opportunity for the application of individualization, modeling, individual approach, including interactive training. The direction of development of information technologies, the optimal use of electronic textbooks, automated training systems, and active training methods for the formation of technical and technological bases allows making fundamental changes in the training process [2].

Аннотация

Для того чтобы образование стало высокоразвитой сферой, общество должно достичь высокого уровня подготовки нового поколения, чтобы обеспечить свое будущее. Это четко отражено в Программе реформ образования Азербайджанской Республики. Для этого содержание образования должно быть обновлено с точки зрения формирования нового общества. Создание новых технологий обучения должно быть реализовано как неотложная задача. Используя возможности интерактивных методов, следует отвести широкое место направлениям, стимулирующим работу учащихся и усиливающим их интерес к обучению и чтению. В модернизации системы образования разнообразное и широкое применение информационных и коммуникационных технологий в процессе обучения открыло большие возможности и перспективы [1].

Кардинальные изменения, происходящие сегодня в человечестве, приводят к приобретению более богатых научных знаний, созданию принципиально новых технологий, необходимости нового педагогического подхода к методике преподавания предметов. При преподавании предметов в школе применение информационно-коммуникационных технологий открывает широкие возможности для применения индивидуализации, моделирования, индивидуального подхода, в том числе интерактивного обучения. Направление развития информационных технологий, оптимальное использование электронных учебников, автоматизированных систем обучения, активных методов обучения для формирования технической и технологической базы позволяет внести принципиальные изменения в учебный процесс [2].

Keywords: *modernization, telecommunications, innovation, technological, interactive training.*

Ключевые слова: модернизация, телекоммуникации, инновации, технологии, интерактивное обучение.

The teaching organization of the training includes software and technology tools that support lectures, course management systems, and computer-based testing systems. First, there is a need for educational software and technology equipment to assist with face-to-face lectures, such as the teaching and learning program

mentioned above. The tools that support lectures in the classroom include LCD projectors, computers, speakers, overhead projectors, etc. includes Another application of ICT in educational organization of training is course management systems. Sometimes called learning management systems, e-learning systems, content

management systems, or learning support systems, they are also applied to computer-based testing systems and teaching organization of learning [3].

In the 20th century, the teacher was the leading source of information, as the educational process was based mainly on traditional learning. In the 21st century, information sources should act as mediators between teachers and students and teach students how to obtain information and effective work methods. This requires improving the technology and content of education. Therefore, higher school teachers should build a work system according to information requirements [5].

A lesson conducted with computer technology and an interactive method is more interesting for students than a traditional lesson. By using these tools, you can arouse great interest in the subject.

One of the directions of innovation is the use of electronic educational resources and modern information technologies in the educational process of the higher school. Computer literacy for teachers is the need of the day and the opportunity to use information and communication technologies should be provided at all times. Wide opportunities have been created in the use of information and communication technologies in higher education institutions of our country [6].

In modern times, the "State Program on reforms in the higher education system of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2009-2013" is being implemented in higher education institutions for integration into the European and world education system. The experience of countries that have made significant progress in the development of education shows that modern, active-interactive training methods based on information and communication technologies, which develop creative thinking and take into account the individual characteristics of the student, give higher results [4].

Internet resources can be used in the process of teaching subjects in several directions:

- a) to make lessons thought-provoking, lively and interesting in order to help students approach the problem of professional training more consciously,
- b) effective teaching of program materials,
- c) to develop students' professional abilities and skills by taking advantage of the teaching, monitoring and checking functions of the computer.

According to experts, the effect created by the Internet and computer in training is very high. The possibilities of the program for visualization of the lesson process are quite wide. The advantages of this program are that the Power Point program has the ability to flawlessly display any video and audio fragments, images, texts, and animation products in front of the audience.

Speaking about the role of ICT in education, we can say that currently information and communication technologies (ICT) are influencing all areas of human life. Thus, ICT is used in workplaces, business, education and entertainment. Today, the development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has a significant impact on the sustainability of education. In this study, factors affecting students' intentions to use information and communication technologies in continuing education, as well as their satisfaction with its

use, were investigated. The purpose of this study is to investigate students' intentions to use information and communication technologies, as well as their satisfaction with such use.

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) have greatly impacted aspects of our lives by increasing the flow of communication and improving the exchange of knowledge. Information and communication technologies (ICT) development has led to countless advantages for individuals. ICT has led to changes in the field of education, changing the way students learn. Physical telecommunication systems and networks in the form of television, mobile, voice, mail, radio and technologies, hardware and software required for collecting, storing, processing and presenting information were used. The sustainability of information and communication technologies (ICT)-enhanced education is defined as the application of information and communication technologies (ICT) in learning and teaching processes that support learning and teaching processes, delivery mechanisms and design parameters for knowledge enhancement.

Information and communication technologies has made a great contribution to the quality of teaching. Such technologies have opened up opportunities to provide personalized instruction using dynamic interactive and engaging content.

It is known that the application of information and communication technologies in education helps to develop competent and efficient problem solving skills in the field of professional activity. Experiences show that students show great interest in using ICT as a source of education. Thus, it is clear that information and communication technologies have become very important pedagogical resources in the innovative approach to teaching and learning processes.

Research over the past decade has shown that computer technology is an effective tool for expanding one's educational opportunities. Research reveals a number of factors that influence teachers' performance.

Today, Azerbaijan, which has successfully stepped on the road to independence, has achieved achievements in the field of educational development as a result of a consistent and sustainable education policy.

The main trend of the 21st century is the wide application of scientific achievements to real life, the development of high technologies, and the informatization of society. The role of information technologies in today's society is very large, and today they occupy a central place in the development of the education system and culture, in the process of intellectualization of society. Its application to various fields of human activity dictates the need for familiarity with information technologies. Science and education are one of the objects of the informatization process of society. The application of information technologies to education requires their correct selection. The active application of information and communication technologies in the field of education should be aimed at increasing the quality and level of specialist training. The application

of information and communication technologies to education should set a goal for the teacher to realize a certain issue:

Realization of the principle of individualization of the lesson process with the condition of maintaining its completeness; helping a person to develop all kinds of cognitive activities; developing the student's way of thinking; activity of acquiring knowledge, skills and habits; All the achievements in the field of application of information and communication technologies to education should serve the development of the methodological basis of the application of information and communication technologies (ICT) to the field of education, the establishment of a telecommunication network, the creation and maintenance of a data and knowledge base. Correct, optimal and harmless use of computers in the educational system is currently a major issue facing society.

Education reform is successfully implemented in Azerbaijan. The improvement of the quality of education, the formation of a developed personality for society, which can meet international standards, is the basis of socio-economic and cultural development. In addition to the family, teachers also have a great responsibility to develop this personality.

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